

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JJUUKO****FIRST NAME: EDRIN****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used the Turabian style for intext referencing

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is not considered akin to a literature review?

- Annotated bibliography.
- Abstract.
- Survey.
- All of these.¹**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Ninth edition, Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2006), 111.

2. A literature review includes:
- Scholarly publications.
 - Previous studies.
 - Research findings.
 - All of these.**²
3. Which of the following are the diagrammatic representations in research?
- Graph.
 - Bar diagram.
 - Pie chart.
 - All of the above.**³
4. The most crucial role played by a reasonable conclusion is:
- It generates the aspects for future research.**⁴
 - It is not a blueprint of the research.
 - It does not summarize the research.
 - It does not pave the way for new research.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid., 103-104.

⁴ Ibid., 110.

5. Which of the following describes the term reliability in research?
- Any research carried out by a person of high repute.
 - When the research outcomes can be generalized in other research settings.
 - Clear definition of research methods to allow for replication of the same.
 - Stability of conceptually designed measures when applied in many scenarios.**⁵
6. Which of the following acts constitute plagiarism?
- To present others' work as own.
 - Paraphrasing without citation.
 - To quote others' work without quotation marks.
 - All of these.**⁶
7. A _____ is a narrative that has the last name of the author and the year of publication. A _____ appears at the research paper's tail end and gives the author's name, publication year, and the title of the source of the article.
- Quotation; citation.
 - Reference list; quotation.
 - Citation; reference list.**⁷
 - Reference list; citation.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Fourth edition, Los Angeles, CA. SAGE publications, Inc, 2018), 473.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 80.

⁷ Ibid., 161- 168.

8. What are the different ways to avoid plagiarism in academic writing?
- Providing references.
 - Citing the original author.
 - Quoting the exact phrase.
 - All of these.** ⁸
9. What is the proper flow of action in academic writing?
- Critical reading- outline- first draft- multiple drafts- final draft- communicate- follow-up.** ⁹
 - Outline-first draft-multiple drafts- final draft- Reading-communicate- follow up.
 - Reading-writing draft-communicate-follow up.
 - Writing the First draft- checking-final draft-communicate- following up.
10. In a research study, _____ is used to combine various approaches in the validation of data, actions, and outcomes:
- Cross validation.
 - Trend analysis.
 - Meta analysis.
 - Triangulation.** ¹⁰

⁸ Ibid., 370.

⁹ Ibid., 23.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 478- 479.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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